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शोधकर्ता सदैव सत्य और ज्ञान की खोज में रहता है। एक शिक्षक के लिए तो शोध उसका जीवन प्राण है क्योंकि शोध उसकी जिज्ञासा को शांत रखता है। यह कहना गलत न होगा कि शिक्षकों, छात्रों, प्रशासकों और राजनीतिज्ञों आदि के लिए अत्यन्त महत्वपूर्ण है क्योंकि ये विभिन्न समस्याओं का सुनियोजित समाधान प्रस्तुत करता है।

सभी लेखकों, पाठकों, शिक्षकों शोध छात्रों, सम्पादकों और सहयोगियों को उच्च शिक्षा की गुणवत्ता के इस पावन यज्ञ में हमारा साथ देने के लिए हम धन्यवाद देते हैं।

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